

Supplementary Material

1 Other Hyperparameter Investigations

We investigate the effects of the weight λ in Equation 3 and the number of matched query samples k in Equation 9. These hyper-parameters are selected based on their influence on the classification accuracy achieved on the validation set. The left side of Figure 1 illustrates the influence of varying values of λ , while the right side of Figure 1 demonstrates the impact of different values of k . Notably, the curves for the validation set (in red) and testing set (in blue) both attain their highest accuracy when using the same values of λ (i.e., $\lambda = 1.0$ for 1-shot and $\lambda = 0.9$ for 5-shot settings) and k (i.e., $k = 15$).

Fig. 1. Left: Accuracy trends of the model tested using the validation set (in red) and the testing set (in blue) when varying the values of λ . Right: Accuracy trends of the model tested using the validation set (in red) and the testing set (in blue) when varying the number of matched query samples k .

2 Impact of Cross Domain Setting

The cross-domain scenario presents a considerable challenge in the field of few-shot classification. To deal with the problematic cross-domain classification scenario, we undertake tests on *miniImageNet* \rightarrow CUB. To be specific, we replicate the procedures outlined by Chen et al. [2], which involve training the model on the base classes extracted from the *miniImageNet* dataset, and subsequently evaluate the model’s performance on the novel classes derived from the CUB dataset. Table 1 presents the results obtained by using the ResNet-18 as the backbone, ensuring a equitable comparison. These results show that the proposed RTDC method achieves the highest performance and illustrate that our

Table 1. The 5-way 5-shot classification accuracy (%) for cross-domain setting on *miniImageNet* \rightarrow CUB, along with 95% confidence intervals. "†" indicates that we have re-implemented the method in the same cross-domain scenario. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Method	Transductive Backbone	<i>miniImageNet</i> \rightarrow CUB	
		5-way	5-shot
MAML [3]	✗	ResNet-18	51.34 \pm 0.72
MatchingNet [11]	✗	ResNet-18	53.07 \pm 0.74
ProtoNet [9]	✗	ResNet-18	62.02 \pm 0.70
RelationNet [10]	✗	ResNet-18	57.71 \pm 0.73
baseline [2]	✗	ResNet-18	65.57 \pm 0.70
baseline++ [2]	✗	ResNet-18	62.04 \pm 0.76
SimpleShot [12]	✗	ResNet-18	65.63
Negative-Cosine [4]	✗	ResNet-18	67.03 \pm 0.76
$S2M2_R$ [6]	✗	ResNet-18	70.44 \pm 0.75
DC† [14]	✗	ResNet-18	66.82 \pm 0.17
DDWM† [13]	✗	ResNet-18	71.55 \pm 0.20
LaplacianShot [15]	✓	ResNet-18	66.33
TIM [1]	✓	ResNet-18	71.00
TDO† [5]	✓	ResNet-18	67.91 \pm 0.20
RTDC(Ours)	✓	ResNet-18	73.71 \pm 0.18

approach is adept at handling scenarios where the feature distributions of the base classes and the novel classes exhibit differences. This demonstrates the enhanced capability of our method in handling cross-domain scenarios, and it also suggests the feasibility of estimating the ground-truth covariance of the few-shot class by capturing the main characteristics of the underlying distribution information through the use of the base classes.

Table 2. The 5-way 1-shot classification accuracy (%) on both CUB and *miniImageNet* with different feature extractors (backbones), along with 95% confidence intervals. "†" means that we re-implement the method in the same setting. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Backbone	CUB		<i>miniImageNet</i>	
	baseline† [2]	RTDC(Ours)	baseline† [2]	RTDC(Ours)
Conv-4	46.43 \pm 0.18	50.18 \pm 0.20	39.35 \pm 0.16	46.41 \pm 0.19
Conv-6	53.16 \pm 0.20	58.29 \pm 0.22	43.57 \pm 0.18	53.03 \pm 0.21
ResNet-10	57.11 \pm 0.21	76.31 \pm 0.23	51.18 \pm 0.19	63.63 \pm 0.22
ResNet-18	59.62 \pm 0.21	77.82 \pm 0.22	50.28 \pm 0.18	62.95 \pm 0.23
ResNet-34	61.96 \pm 0.21	79.74 \pm 0.21	50.90 \pm 0.19	63.97 \pm 0.22

3 Performance with Different Backbones

Our approach belongs to fine-tuning-based FSL methods, thus it is agnostic to feature extractors (backbones). Utilizing both CUB and *miniImageNet*, we do comparison experiments in the 5-way 1-shot setup to assess the influence of various backbones. We adopt the same training strategy as the baseline [2] approach to evaluate the effectiveness of our method. Table 2 shows that across

different backbones, our technique consistently outperforms the baseline [2]. In contrast, when compared to the backbones trained by the baseline [2], our approach demonstrates an accuracy improvement of approximately 12% on average. Furthermore, as the backbone’s performance improves, the advantages offered by our method become increasingly evident.

Table 3. The 5-way 1-shot and 5-way 5-shot classification accuracy (%) on CUB and *mini*Imagenet based on RTDC with different classifiers, along with 95% confidence intervals. SVM: Support Vector Machine, GNB: Gaussian Naive Bayes, LR: Logistic Regression. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Classifier	CUB		<i>mini</i> Imagenet	
	5-way 1-shot	5-way 5-shot	5-way 1-shot	5-way 5-shot
SVM [7]	89.42 ± 0.17	93.78 ± 0.09	77.56 ± 0.21	88.37 ± 0.12
GNB [7]	89.29 ± 0.17	93.69 ± 0.09	76.93 ± 0.21	87.55 ± 0.13
LR [7]	89.49 ± 0.17	94.19 ± 0.08	77.61 ± 0.21	88.99 ± 0.12

4 Performance with Different Classifiers

Our proposed method aims to alleviate the data scarcity problem by generating samples from learned feature distributions and thus can be applied with any classification model. We do comparison experiments in both 5-way 1-shot and 5-way 5-shot scenarios on CUB and *mini*ImageNet to explore the effect of different classifiers. Table 3 presents the results of the proposed RTDC method on Support Vector Machine (SVM), Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB), and Logistic Regression (LR) classifiers trained with the samples from the learned distributions. All the three classification models are implemented using scikit-learn [7]. As can be seen from the results, their accuracy is comparable, which indicates that our method is not sensitive to the classification model and that good results can be achieved using a simple logistic regression classifier.

5 Performance with High-ways and High-shots

To investigate the influence of the high-ways and high-shots settings in our method, we do experiments in three distinct settings, similar to the previous studies [2, 6, 5].

First, we conduct experiments by varying the number of support classes (support ways) in the support set. In this specific analysis, we vary the support ways, considering values of 10, 15, and 20, while keeping the number of query samples per novel class fixed at 15. Table 4 presents the related results, showing that the proposed RTDC method outperforms the other approaches by a significant margin. It can be seen that our RTDC outperforms TDO [5] by around 5% (1-shot) and 6% (5-shot). The TDO [5] method also introduces a transductive manner

Table 4. Accuracy (%) of varying the number of support ways on *miniImageNet* of 600 FSL tasks. "†" means that we re-implement the method in the high-way setting. "*" indicates that the results are presented in previous work [6]. The best results are highlighted in bold.

Method	10-way		15-way		20-way	
	1-shot	5-shot	1-shot	5-shot	1-shot	5-shot
baseline++ [2]	40.43	56.89	31.96	48.20	26.92	42.80
LEO* [8]	45.26	64.36	36.74	56.26	31.42	50.48
<i>S2M2R</i> [6]	50.40	70.93	41.65	63.32	36.50	58.36
DC† [14]	52.49	72.86	44.64	66.11	39.28	61.24
DDWM† [13]	53.21	74.39	45.10	67.71	39.99	62.80
TDO† [5]	55.18	74.04	46.08	66.59	40.15	61.51
RTDC(Ours)	61.22	78.80	52.40	72.37	46.46	67.52

Fig. 2. Left: Accuracy trends with varying the number of support shots when applying (in red) or not applying (in blue) the proposed method. Right: Accuracy trends with varying the number of query shots.

to estimate the distributions, but it primarily focuses on directly deriving the distribution from the selected data using the Euclidean metric. In contrast to it, we incorporate the base classes to facilitate the ground-truth covariance of the few-shot class and utilize the Mahalanobis distance to explore the influence of the feature distribution further, resulting in improved performance.

Furthermore, we conduct experiments by varying the number of labeled samples for each novel class (support shots) in the support set. In specific, the number of support shots ranged from 1 to 20 in these experiments, with the number of query samples per class fixed at 15. The left side of Figure 2 illustrates the accuracy trend when varying the number of support shots, both with (in red) and without (in blue) applying the proposed method. It is noticeable that our method consistently improves performance, with a more significant improvement when the number of support shots is lower. This underlines the effectiveness of our method when dealing with scenarios with limited labeled samples.

Next, we conduct experiments by varying the number of unlabeled samples for each novel class (query shots) in the query set. Since the CUB dataset has

a variable count of examples in each class, with the smallest class having only 41 examples, we only show the experimental results for different query shots on the *miniImageNet*, *tieredImageNet* and CIFAR-FS datasets. We systematically vary the number of query shots from 5 to 240, keeping the number of support shots fixed at 1. To make use of a larger number of unlabeled samples in the transductive setting, we set k to match the number of query shots. The right side of Figure 2 demonstrates that the performance of our method steadily improves as the number of query shots increases, eventually stabilizing when the number of query shots exceeds 90. Given our method’s capability to determine the ground-truth covariance of the few-shot class and select the most appropriate unlabeled samples to calibrate the class center based on that covariance, it can effectively utilize unlabeled sample information in a transductive manner.

References

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